

ARTS

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF COLORS IN DESIGN

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Abstract

This article discusses the problems of color science. As you know, colors play an important role in solving aesthetic problems of creative activity in design and visual arts. From this point of view, this work analyzes the physical properties of flowers, as well as their psycho-emotional impact on a man.

The article deals with the scientific and theoretical views on flowers, some well-known experts in different historical periods. Summarizing the materials studied and based on personal practical experience, the author provides a color classification. On its basis, the use of colors in artistic activities is commented, at the same time, the importance of optimization in this matter is noted.

The article, among other things, deals with the possibility of using colors in the organization of *man-object-machine-environment* systems with a utilitarian-functional purpose.

We hope that the presented scientific article, being the result of our serious research in the field of color research, will be of value in the future in conducting scientific research in this direction.

Keywords: color, theory, design, psychophysiology, method, classification

1. INTRODUCTION

Even from ancient times, people became interested in color and used them in everyday life - dwellings, clothes, objects. Colors, along with their aesthetic meaning in the life of ancient people, also expressed their mythological worldview, religious and ideological views in one form or another, and then, at different stages of social life, also had sociocultural significance.

Color and color schemes have been studied from time to time and have become a separate area of research. It should be noted that the problem of color was also the subject of research by ancient philosophers and thinkers. Famous Greek philosophers Plato, Aristotle and others conducted research in this area. Their scientific work played a role in the further study of colors.

The thoughts and conclusions about the psychological peculiarities of colors by Russian scientist

M.V.Lomonosov, English scientist I. Newton, German philosopher V. Hote, wellknown painter, graphicist, theorist and pedagogy V. Kandinsky, Francis specialist of technicalaesthetic J. Veneno, Francis scientists M. Deribere, Russian psychologist V. M. Bekhterev, Switzerland psychologist M. Lüscher and etc. assume very high importance in the chromatics science. Put forward thoughts and conclusions have played very important role in the mainly investigation and study of colours, including in their practical application opportunities in different spheres too [9, p. 116-117].

Cording to the scientific literature, there are three of the four primary colors that are considered major - red, yellow and blue; and one is green, obtained by mixing colors. The determined color system is shown in the following diagram (scheme1) [6, p.107].

Scheme1.

The colours divide into chromate - coloured (in Greek ori- gin means – “chromos” – colour) and achromatic-colourless types. In the scientific specialists literatures yellow, orange, red, blue, cyan, green, violet and other many colour shades includes to chromatic

colours, these colours have characteristics of colours [12, p.87]. Achromatic colors include white, black, gray and their different (dark, light) shades (scheme2).

Scheme 2.

The main characteristics of the color are determined in the following sequence:

- color tone - color property;
- saturation - color quality;
- lightness - the quality of the observed color, built up by the sensation of a greater or lesser degree of relative brightness.

First of all, prominent English physicist and mathematician Isaac Newton explained the colours nature. He defined visible light as a physical factor in the perception of all colors. He showed that white sun shining

joins seven different colours on itself. They are red, orange, yellow, green, cyan (blue), indigo (blue) and violet.

From all these colours' junctions creates the white colour. We should note that red, blue and yellow of those seven colours consider the main colours. Being different from I. Newton, as a poet V. Hote attracted by colours' romance and their influence peculiarities to human's sentiment. He wrote: "The colours can create the emotions on humans ...". Conditionally he divided

on colours into two groups – bringing happiness and cause of sad and investigated them separately [18, p. 62].

Jack Veneno the founder of Technical Aesthetic Institution of France the professional specialists on colours' climate wrote: "The colours are very capable: it can make calmness and irritant light. It can create the harmony and shock; we can expect from them both miracle and commotion" [1, p.37]. Another Francis scientist M. Deribere separately analyzed the different colours' viewpoint of psychology and showed that they directly influenced to the act and humans' health [1, p. 39-40]. The emotional – psychological peculiarities of colour, natural influences and importance has explained in another source too [20]. V. M. Bekhterev the famous psychologist generalized all his experience on colour's influence to organism and come to such conclusion that in the future would be efficiently used from the colours in treatment of nervous diseases. In some scientific works by Timiryaze was about the colours and their emotional and psychological reacts on humans [17, p.129].

The humans with higher skin and optic sense can even determine the colours with their fingers. The humans with higher skin and optic sense can even determine the colours with their fingers. After many practical experiments carried out by ourselves we got know that such "definition" is obviously possible in special position of organism.

Formerly, such interesting experience was created out on the students of the department of "Artistic drawing" in the chair of "Pedagogy and psychology" of the Pedagogical Institute in Nizhny Taghil. Mainly, the same ability was discovered on ten of fifteen students [19, p.64].

Switzerland psychologist Max Lüscher offered the colours' tests which were methods for analyzing of personality and at the same time formed complete direction on the science about the colours [11, p.108].

In the creativity on different types and genres of fine art the colours are one of the most powerful influential means and is investigated and studied their different shades of artistic-aesthetic, emotional-psychological and semantic peculiarities in according level, but in the technical aesthetics and in design creativity the investigation and their studies according to their physical and psychological properties and influences beside above-mentions assume very high importance. Because, in different spheres of design creativity optimal application of colours and the main problems on appointment of objects and things create effective warranty for composition of utilitarian - functional and psychophysiological requirements.

As we noted in design creativity one of the main problems are the creation of welfare things and equipment, including utensils also the organization problem of interior and exterior. In the organization of *human-thing-machine- environment* systems the ergonomic factors belonging to the part of composition of architectural design in the organization of interior – beside with anthropometric, biomechanics, hygienic, lighting and etc. problems, the purposely expression of aesthetic and psychophysiological viewpoint of colours, especially should be in the focus of attention. Thus, the specific

peculiarities of colours can make according psychological correction in interior – space environment. At the same time, the colours can make according correction in environmental view of things. For example, the imagination about their object heaviness (of course, illusion), can be created by their colours being different from their natural heaviness. Thus, the light colour that is used in interior (of course, in according level) also the things consisting of light colours create very comfortable and wide space environment influence. But dark colours contrary create rather narrow environment condition and make to be born and tired. These assume according psychophysiological problems too. Taking into attention the same problems, in interior, especially in the spheres being close to the roots, including in the decoration of things (chandelier, decorative curtains, decorative wallpapers) placing in more attractive spheres would be better to use from light colours and from their shades too. It also creates suitable conditions for effective lighting. In generally, in an interior arrangement however to use less dark colours on different things and equipment it would be optimized more effective lightning. At the present-day, in the markets we can see many curtains' samples that on their white background have used from black or dark brown colours' with different forms of elements, also from compositions with botanical ornaments. Of course, such decoration is tasteless, at the same time; with its "heavy" view would be always make eyes to get tired.

The observations shows that for recently, not the only in welfare things and utensils, including in different polygraphic samples prefers to use from red colours too. Of cause, such approach intended for more attraction of things and for advertise their. But, we must take into attention that utilization from things with red colour in the interior for a long time would create psychological tiredness on human. As it is known, the wave length of red colour in the spectre is longer (620-800 nm) and has irritative influence. The same colour is differing from other colours for its psychoemotional peculiarities and its symbolic essence. The broad conclusions about its peculiarities have generalized as following: "Be careful with red colour" [16, p.55]. According to experts in the design solution, it is not recommended to use red furniture in the kitchen and in the bedroom. Because, person rests in the bedroom and so that it would be better to use from calming colours. In another source shows that for red, orange and yellow colours influence the breath becomes deepen and pulse becomes more speeders; but from the influence of green, blue and cyan colours occur opposite influence. So that first group of colours' considers as calming colours' [15, p.223].

In the work environment, in industrial condition utilization from right colors harmony straighten the labor activity and prevents physical tiredness. Formerly, the American scientist F. Birren basically was busy with the same problem.

However, taking into attention many objects, especially, the complication level of provision with things and equipment, the appointment of environment in interior organization both in complex form, also in things and equipment also in design solution of interior

during the colours appointment we must prefer such colours which eliminates the tiredness and gives psychological calmness and including the colours' harmony of the nature. Of course, here have some exceptions too. For example, we have such objects (medical, military, fire stations and etc.) that there uses from special colours and from their shades in their things and equipment, including in their interior and exterior. They are based on serious terms and such special colours regulates with the international standards.

In the creation of *human-thing-machine-environment* systems, during the arrangement, instead of the colours' application is dominating aesthetic viewpoint, during some special situations they are intended for utilitarian and functional purposes and are according to these requirements. For example, such informational colour constantly regulates the motions of drivers and foot passengers on the traffic lights. In different institutions, objects, in things and equipment, clothes and etc. widely uses from informational colours. Informational colours, basically has determined in two categories. Here basically considers-red, yellow, green; auxiliary are orange and blue colours [10, p.108]. Even, in the ancient Japan, colours played a role of exactly information bearer [16, p.40].

2. METHODS

Purposely utilization of colours viewpoint of functionality assumes importance not only in any of acting processes, at the same time it assumes importance in things appointment tendencies. Choosing of colours on functionality can create the ergonomic guarantees of utilitarian for condition, environment and time (day and night) on intended objects, things and equipment. This problem is quite accurately solved by instinct in various living beings (for disguise). In this sense, we have yet to learn from nature and its creatures. It means, in the *human-thing-machine-environment* systems, for acting processes viewpoint of functionality the colours should meet ergonomic requirement too. The ergonomic choosing of colours, depending on functionality appointment, contest and the requirement level of things can be based on relative contrast colours for harmony or contrasting. The same problems have to solve seriously and in necessary level but not relatively. For example, electric torch (Camelion ® Super Bright) made in Germany, meets the highest utilitarian and functional requirements for its material quality, form and according to its ergonomics texture. But, its electric torch is in black colour and so that to find it in dark room (even, it is near) is very difficult. In the same thing, viewpoint of functionality has relatively given the ergonomic colour chosen. However, the switch and bulb are yellow and the bulb's diameter is 2 mm. and these indicators creates relatively guarantee for its utilization in darkness. But, if we consider that the switch is not near the user in completely dark space so, for its finding the thin yellow colour of bulb does not completely guarantee the usability. It would be better the corpus of electric torch was yellow, the switch was yellow, the switch and bulb was red, or the corpus was light green, and the switch and bulb was in orange. We should note that there are enough yellow electric torches belonging to the German production in the markets. We just wanted to

analyze one of our using things as a sample viewpoint of utilitarian – functional requirements usability and to give to your attentions [7, p. 174-178].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As it is known, even since the previous time have used from colours in the samples of decorative - applied art, and in decoration of interior and exterior and for other purposes. At the present-day, beside utilization from colours in the creativity, specially their application became to be in the focus of attention. And we partially tried to analyze some applied problems of colours in design and in some publications and monograph [5, p.4-7; 6, p.105-109; 8, p.80-85; 9, p. 114-133].

The creation of *human-thing-machine-environment* systems and perceiving of colours in its organization and their psychological influence to humans have seriously investigated by the specialists, and achieved interesting results in this aspect. It is natural that under the modern condition uses from opportunities of chromatics science not only in the solution of artistic-esthetic assignment of interior and exterior, it also uses widely in industrial design-in decoration of things and equipment. Of course, the projecting ware of designer who deeply investigated the problems of colours problems and correctly used their application will be always attract the attention and ensure the tastes of buyers.

4. SUMMARY

The problems about the semantic and psychophysiological influence of colours were based and explained in different scientific-specialists literatures in according level [1; 2; 3; 4; 10; 12; 13; 14; 16; 18; 20]. On the base of scientific-theoretical conclusions, also on the base of individual observations and experience the colours can be classified according to physical properties and psychological-emotional influences on different groups (main colours, derivate colours) as following [9, p. 130]:

- chromatic-achromatic;
- hot-cold;
- active-passive;
- dark-light;
- vivid-weighed;
- contrast-relative;
- optimist-pessimist;
- irritative -calmness;
- symbolic and etc.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In industrial design, in industrial graphic, advertisement, artistic bundle, artistic encase and etc. creative works, the classification of colours application with taking into the consideration the different and multi-sided peculiarities could create effective guarantee to the solution of general composition viewpoint of visual requests of artistic-aesthetic, psychological-emotional and usability.

The creation of *human-thing-machine-environment* system and in its organization the advisable utili-

zation of them according to their psychological influence, including their artistic-aesthetic expression opportunities as the result would increase comfortableness aesthetic value of object.

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